

Tritium transport modeling at system level for the EUROfusion Dual Coolant Lithium-Lead breeding blanket

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Abstract. The Dual Coolant Lithium Lead breeding blanket is one of the four breeder blanket concepts under consideration within the framework of EUROfusion consortium activities. The aim of this work is to develop a model that can dynamically track tritium concentrations and fluxes along each part of the DCLL blanket and the ancillary systems associated to it at any time. Because of tritium nature, the phenomena of diffusion, dissociation, recombination and solubilisation have been modeled in order to describe the interaction between the lead-lithium channels, the structural materials, the Flow Channel Inserts and the helium channels that are present in the breeding blanket. The simulations have been performed using the object oriented modeling software EcosimPro. Results have been obtained for a pulsed generation scenario for DEMO. The tritium inventory in different parts of the blanket, the permeation rates from the breeder to the secondary coolant and the amount of tritium extracted from the lead-lithium loop have been computed.

Keywords: Transport Modeling, Tritium, DCLL, DEMO

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1. Introduction

Due to the very limited reserve of tritium, future D-T fusion power plants must be conceived to ensure their tritium self-sufficiency. The breeding blankets are systems designed among other functions to regenerate tritium. They have to be able to carry the tritium out of the reactor for its future reinjection in the plasma. Tritium transport models aims to provide accurate descriptions of the tritium behavior in the breeding blankets and its auxiliary systems helping with the design activities of such systems. Moreover, since tritium is a beta emitter, the estimations of tritium inventories along the different parts of the system are important from the perspective of the plant safety.

In the framework of the EUROfusion consortium programme, tritium transport models at both system level and breeder zone level are being developed for the four breeding blanket concepts under consideration which are: Helium Cooled Lithium Lead (HCLL), Water Cooled Lithium Lead (WCLL), Helium Cooled Pebble Bed (HCPB) and the Dual Coolant Lithium Lead (DCLL) [1]. System level models for the WCLL concept [2] and for the HCPB concept [3] have been already developed using the object oriented simulation tool EcosimPro [4]. In the present work, the same simulation tool and methodology have been used for developing a tritium transport model at system level for the DCLL concept.

The model has provided results of tritium inventory inside the different parts of the blanket and its ancillary system. The extraction rate of tritium in the Tritium Extraction System (TES) has been also calculated. Besides, the permeation of tritium from the breeder material to the secondary coolant circuits has been computed. This last result is of special interest for evaluating the tritium self-sufficiency of the reactor and also for safety reasons.

Finally, a parametric study has been performed in order to analyze other scenarios which can be relevant for the designs of the breeding blanket and its ancillary systems. The influence of two key parameters, the lead-lithium mass flow rate and the TES efficiency, have been studied independently in order to analyze their impact over the whole system. In addition, a DCLL model without Flow Channel Inserts (FCIs) has been considered in order to better understand how this crucial component affects the tritium behavior.

2. System description

The DCLL blanket is based on eutectic PbLi as neutron multiplier and tritium breeder. In this blanket concept, the lead-lithium acts not only as breeder but also as the primary coolant. For this reason the liquid metal is flowing at much higher velocities

($\sim 1\text{cm/s}$) than other liquid metal based breeding blanket concepts. The high velocities that characterize the DCLL cause heavy magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) effects. The MHD pressure drop is mitigated by including FCIs [5] in the channels. The blanket design also includes helium for cooling the structure. This is made of reduced-activation ferritic-martensitic steel (EUROFER). The design of EU-DCLL is on progress, the assessments here presented are based on the design published in [6].

The design activities focus on the outboard equatorial module as it is considered the most representative one of the blanket and supports the highest neutronic and thermal loads. The outboard equatorial module of the DCLL blanket is divided into four parallel circuits in toroidal direction. In each circuit the liquid metal flows following the path shown in figure 1. The helium flows in small rectangular channels drilled in the stiffening plates (radial and toroidal), in the first wall (FW) and in the side walls of the module. The modules inside one segment are attached to a common back supporting structure (BSS) whose function is not only sustaining the structure but also feeding the modules with helium and lead-lithium.

Figure 1. (left) Toroidal section of the outboard equatorial module and schematic of the PbLi circuit layout; (right) poloidal section of the outboard equatorial module showing the breeding zone, the back supporting structure (BSS), the He manifold zone and the first wall (FW)

The FCIs considered in the EU-DCLL consist in two layers of EUROFER and one layer of alumina in between forming a sandwich structure [7]. The thickness of the insert is 1.1 mm in total; 0.5 mm each steel layer and 0.1 mm the alumina layer. The FCIs are not directly attached to the structure walls but in between them there is a 2 mm wide gap filled with lead-lithium. The objective of the gap is to accommodate the FCI inside the lead-lithium flow avoiding the appearance of mechanical stresses in the FCI derived from the different thermal deformation of the structural walls and the FCI. Therefore, the FCI

is embedded in the lead-lithium separating the flow in two zones: the so called "bulk flow" which it is assumed to carry the 97.5 % of the mass flow and "gap flow" which it is assumed to carry the 2.5% of the mass flow. Figure 2 shows an schematic view of a DCLL channel section where the bulk flow, the FCI, the gap flow and the structure walls with the helium channels can be distinguished.

Figure 2. Schematic cross section of a lead-lithium channel showing the bulk flow, the FCI, the gap flow, the EUROFER wall and the He channels

The tritium model described here includes the effect of the characteristic MHD velocity profile in the bulk flow and the effects of the FCIs and the gap flows. All of them are essential to correctly compute and understand the tritium behavior inside the DCLL system.

The DCLL blanket is divided in sixteen sectors according to the European DEMO2014 layout [1]. Each sector is fed by a lead-lithium pumping system; thus, there are 16 lead-lithium loops feeding the blanket [8]. The design of the DCLL is modular; in each sector of the blanket there are 14 inboard breeder modules and 24 outboard breeder modules. The inboard modules are grouped in 2 multi-module segments of 7 modules each and the outboard modules are grouped in three multi-module segments of 8 modules each.

Each lead-lithium loop in the system has several auxiliary and control systems [8]. Three of those systems, the TES, the heat exchanger and the pump have been taken into account for the tritium transport model.

The TES is placed outside the reactor and it is connected in series immediately after the blanket. The design of this system is still under study. A conceptual analysis have shown that a TES based on the permeation against vacuum technique could operate with an extraction efficiency of an 80% at relevant DCLL conditions [9]. This value has been taken as the reference one for the present calculations.

The lead-lithium loops include heat exchangers for the power conversion. This device is connected in series

Figure 3. Toroidal section view of the DCLL DEMO TOKAMAK showing the 16 sectors and one of the PbLi loops, including its main components

in between the TES and the blanket. Its design is still in an early stage, only one numerical analysis has been performed so far [10]. The dimensions used for that study has been taken as the reference for the present tritium transport model in the absence of other input data. The heat exchanger considered in the transport model is a straight tube that uses water as secondary coolant. It has a contact area of 21.8 m² and a volume of 31.7 m³.

3. Model description

Any system level model requires some assumptions and simplifications. It is out of the scope of this kind of models to provide very detailed local results. Instead, by sacrificing some local precision the model is able to represent reliably the global behavior of the whole system without spending too many computational resources.

From this perspective, the tritium transport model of the DCLL blanket has been programmed under the assumption that all the blanket modules are equal. According to this simplification it is possible to compute the evolution of tritium concentration and the tritium fluxes in one outboard equatorial module and then multiply the results by the total number of modules fed by one lead-lithium loop. This assumption is conservative from the point of view of safety because the equatorial modules are the biggest ones of the blanket; thus, they will retain more tritium inventory than the others. Figure 4 depicts the Process Flow Diagram (PFD) used for modeling one of the 16 lead-lithium loops which feeds 38 modules of the blanket. The tritium is generated in the blanket and then dragged out of the system by the lead-lithium flow. After that it goes through the TES where most of it is extracted. The remaining tritium goes through the heat exchanger before re-entering the blanket closing

the loop.

Part of the tritium produced inside the lead-lithium channels can permeate through the structure walls and reach the helium circuit. The assessment of this permeation rate is of special interest because of safety reasons and also to guarantee the tritium self-sufficiency of the reactor.

Figure 4. PFD of one of the 16 lead-lithium loops in the DCLL blanket

Instead of providing an accurate but computationally expensive 3D description of the outboard equatorial module, this system level model has been developed using 1D components that communicate between each other dynamically following a PFD. Figure 5 depicts the PFD used for modeling each parallel circuit of the DCLL module. Each box of the PFD computes the tritium concentration and tritium fluxes evolutions using 1D equations. The lead-lithium, helium and the water flows are discretized along the axial direction of each duct. In contrast, the EUROFER walls and the alumina layer are also discretized along the direction normal to their surfaces which is the tritium permeation direction. Using this technique it is possible to approximate the tritium behavior in a complex 3D geometry like the breeder module using 1D equations.

The lead-lithium channels that appear in the module PFD cannot be modeled using a simple 1D flow. Due to the MHD interactions, a liquid metal flow under a strong transverse magnetic field in a duct with electrical insulating walls develops an almost flat velocity profile with thin boundary layers next to the walls [5, 11]. The thickness of these layers is different for the walls parallel to the magnetic field (Side layers) and for the walls perpendicular to the magnetic field (Hartmann layers). In both types of layers the lead-lithium is essentially stagnant. Besides, the channel has to include the two lead-lithium flows separated by the FCI. Figure 6 depicts the PFD of a lead-lithium squared section channel which includes the bulk flow, the MHD boundary layers, the FCI materials and the gap flow.

In the design of the DCLL there are multiple

Figure 5. PFD of one of the 4 parallel circuits of the breeder module

Figure 6. PFD of one lead-lithium channel

helium channels drilled in the walls. Nevertheless, those channels have been approximated with a single helium flow sandwiched between two EUROFER layers. The contact area between the steel and the helium has been corrected in order to minimize the effect of this approximation. The value of the correction factor depends on the kind of wall: 1.55 for the FW, 1.7 for the toroidal stiffening plates and 1.65 for the radial stiffening plates and side walls. Those factors have been taken from previous 2D calculations of tritium permeation in this kind of geometries [12]. The PFD of one helium cooled wall is shown in figure 7.

The three systems considered have been modeled

in the following way. The TES and the pump have been modeled as black boxes that introduce some equations directly in the loop PFD (figure 4). The heat exchanger has been described using the PFD shown in figure 7. It consists on a flow of lead-lithium and a flow of water separated by a membrane of steel.

Figure 7. (left) PFD of any structure wall (stiffening plate, first wall and side walls); (right) PFD of the heat exchanger

4. Mathematical model

The elementary boxes of the PFDs have associated a series of dynamical and algebraic equations that have to be computed at every time step. When tritium is dissolved inside the lead-lithium, tritium concentration ($c_{\text{PbLi}}(t, x_i)$) is governed by (1). This 1D equation contains the phenomena of advection, diffusion, generation and permeation.

$$\partial_t c_{\text{PbLi}}(t, x_i) = -\frac{u(x_{i+1})c_{\text{PbLi}}(t, x_{i+1})}{\Delta x} + \frac{u(x_i)c_{\text{PbLi}}(t, x_i)}{\Delta x} + G(t, x_i) - \frac{J_n(t, x_i)}{\Delta x} \quad (1)$$

Δx is the discretization length, x_i is the position of the i -th node, $u(x_i)$ is the axial component of the velocity of the lead-lithium and $J_n(t, x_i)$ is the component of the tritium flux normal to the channel walls at the i -th node.

The function $G(t, x_i)$ represents the generation of tritium inside the liquid metal. It has been decomposed into a temporal component and a spatial component. The temporal component is given by the DEMO reactor pulses [13] while the spatial component follows an exponential profile along the radial direction and a constant profile along the poloidal and toroidal directions, as shown in (2).

$$G(t, r) = G_t(t) p \exp(-b(r - \omega)) \quad (2)$$

The shape of the spatial profile has been picked motivated by the neutronics studies of the DCLL blanket [14,15]. According to these data, the radial values inside a module have a quasi exponential decrease as shown in figure 8. The toroidal symmetry of the tokamak implies a constant toroidal profile.

Along the poloidal direction the generation varies for the different modules of a segment. However, in the short poloidal range of one module, this profile can be considered uniform [14]. As a consequence, a uniform generation profile along the poloidal direction has been imposed when applying the simplification which assumes that every module is equal in the blanket. That way, the parameters p and ω have been chosen by normalizing (2) to the total generation of the blanket while the parameter b has been picked as the result of the best fitting of the neutronic data.

Figure 8. Tritium production radial profile in the outboard equatorial module.

Inside the structural walls and the FCI materials tritium concentration evolves affected only by diffusion. The diffusion flux points to the concentration gradient direction which is mainly the direction normal to the contact surface. The tritium flux and tritium concentration inside the materials follows (3) and (4) respectively.

$$J_y(t, x_i, y_j) = -D \frac{c_{\text{mat}}(t, x_i, y_j) - c_{\text{mat}}(t, x_i, y_{j-1})}{\Delta y} \quad (3)$$

$$\partial_t c_{\text{mat}}(t, x_i, y_j) = -\frac{J_y(t, x_i, y_{j+1}) - J_y(t, x_i, y_j)}{\Delta y} \quad (4)$$

$c_{\text{mat}}(t, x_i, y_j)$ is the concentration of tritium inside the material, y_j is the position of the j -th node along the direction normal to the surface of the material, Δy is the distance between the nodes, x_i is the position of the i -th node along the axial direction of the lead-lithium (or helium) flow, $J_y(t, x_i, y_j)$ is the normal component of the diffusion flux and D is the diffusivity constant of tritium in the material.

Concerning the surface processes, inside the lead-lithium, the alumina and the EUROFER, tritium is present in its atomic form. As a consequence, there is neither recombination nor dissociation at the interfaces between any of those materials. The system tends to

Table 1. Macroscopic constants of tritium in the materials of interest

	EUROFER	PbLi	Alumina
$D_0(\text{m}^2/\text{s})$	$2.64 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$4.03 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$2.90 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Ea (kJ/mol)	-22.30	-19.50	-198.71
$K_{S_0}(\text{mol}/\text{Pa}^{0.5}\text{m}^3)$	$2.25 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$	189.79
Ea (kJ/mol)	-15.10	-1.35	-119.50
$K_{r_0}(\text{m}^4/\text{mol s})$	$2.84 \cdot 10^{-7}$	—	—
Ea (kJ/mol)	28.68	—	—
$K_{d_0}(\text{mol}/\text{Pa s m}^2)$	$2.99 \cdot 10^{-8}$	—	—
Ea (kJ/mol)	-29.23	—	—

balance the partial pressures at both sides of this kind of interfaces. According to Henry's law, this introduces a discontinuity in the concentration, as shown in (5).

$$\frac{c_{\text{PbLi}}}{K_{\text{SPbLi}}} = \frac{c_{\text{mat}}}{K_{\text{Smat}}} \quad (5)$$

K_{Smat} and K_{SPbLi} are the solubility constants of tritium in the material and in lead-lithium respectively. The properties of the hydrogen isotopes in EUROFER [16], alumina [17, 18] and lead-lithium [19] have been obtained from experimental measures. The value of the macroscopic constants are summarized in table 1. They follow an Arrhenius-like dependence with the temperature.

Most of experimental works use hydrogen or deuterium instead of tritium. When tritium experiments are not available for the materials of interest the hydrogen measurements have been taken. The classical mass dependence has been used for the EUROFER diffusivity which states that the pre-exponential factor is proportional to $1/\sqrt{m}$ where m = mass of diffusing atom [20]. For the solubility and for recombination and dissociation coefficients there is no classical dependence available.

In the references [16–18] the solubility is obtained indirectly. The diffusivity (D) and permeability (ϕ) are obtained directly from the experiments while the solubility is obtained using the relation between the three constants (6).

$$\phi = D \cdot K_s \quad (6)$$

There are several experimental measures of the lead-lithium solubility in the literature that differs orders of magnitude from each other. Previous models [21] have shown the heavy impact that this constant has over the tritium permeation. In the present model, the lowest value available for the lead-lithium solubility [19] has been taken as a reference. This decision is conservative in terms of permeation

because according to (5) the lowest lead-lithium solubility will imply the highest permeation.

In [19] the pre-exponential value is given in $\text{at.fr}/\text{Pa}^{0.5}$. To make the conversion to the SI units the model uses the density of lead-lithium which depends linearly with the temperature [22]. The value depicted in table 1 corresponds to the density at $T = 400$ °C.

Inside the helium flow, tritium is no longer present in its atomic form but in its molecular form: T_2 . The concentration of T_2 inside the fluid (c_{T_2}) follows an equation very similar to (1) although in this case the source term comes from the permeation through the EUROFER-helium interface.

$$\partial_t c_{T_2}(t, x_i) = -\frac{u(x_{i+1})c_{T_2}(t, x_{i+1}) - u(x_i)c_{T_2}(t, x_i)}{\Delta x} + \frac{J_{m_{T_2}}(t, x_i)}{\Delta x} \quad (7)$$

The molecular flux, J_m , that enters or leaves the helium flow can be written in terms of the constants of recombination (K_r) and dissociation (K_d) at the interface between the EUROFER and the coolant as shown in (8). The value of those constants (table 1) have been taken from experimental measures [23].

$$J_{m_{T_2}} = K_d p_{T_2} - K_r (c_T)^2 \quad (8)$$

p_{T_2} is the partial pressure of the gas dissolved inside the coolant and c_T is the atomic concentration of tritium in the EUROFER. With this description it is not assumed neither a diffusion limited process nor a surface limited process, the regime depends on the specific values of the constants and the concentrations.

As described in section 2 and shown in figure 4, in order to fully describe the complete lead-lithium loop it is necessary to take into account the effect of the TES and the heat exchanger. The TES is placed outside of the blanket and it has been described as a black box that extracts tritium with certain efficiency η following (9).

$$c(t)_{\text{out}} = (1 - \eta)c(t)_{\text{in}} \quad (9)$$

The PFD of the heat exchanger is shown in figure 7. It has been assumed that the components needed for the heat exchanger PFD are not different from the ones used for the rest of the model, thus no new equations are needed. The last component of the PFD is a pumping system that imposes a constant mass flow rate of lead-lithium.

In order to solve the total system of differential/algebraic equations, the object oriented modeling software EcosimPro proceeds in the following way. Firstly, based on certain initial values for tritium concentrations (typically zero) the model computes the

fluxes and surface concentrations by solving the algebraic system formed by (3), (5), (8) and (9). Straightaway, according to those fluxes the temporal derivatives of the concentrations in the different components are obtained using (1), (4) and (7). With a numerical integration of those three equations the concentrations after a certain Δt are computed. Those new concentrations allow computing the new fluxes and concentration derivatives. This method is used recursively in order to obtain the tritium concentrations and fluxes at any time in the different components. The DASSL algorithm [24] has been used for solving the system of differential/algebraic equations. It uses the backward differentiation formula for integrating the derivatives and the Newton-Raphson method for solving the algebraic systems of equations.

5. 3D model comparison

Even though the developed of a detailed 3D transport model of the DCLL outboard equatorial model is out of the scope of this work, it is of interest to perform a comparison between the results of a 3D calculation and the system level results. This way, it is possible to obtain an estimation of the uncertainty that the approximations of the system level model are introducing in the results.

For this purpose, a 3D tritium transport stationary calculation of a square section lead-lithium channel has been performed. The dimensions of the channel are 0.15 m side and 2 m length while the channel walls are 15 mm thick. For simplicity, only viscous effects have been considered in the flow equations. In this system, there is a fixed tritium concentration at the inlet c_0 . Tritium is dragged by the lead-lithium flow and it permeates through the EUROFER walls that surrounds the liquid metal. At the other side of the walls, a zero concentration boundary conditions have been imposed. The simulation has been launched using the simulation platform ANSYS-FLUENT.

The results obtained in this computation are exposed in figure 9 and figure 10. In those figures the concentration and velocity boundary layers can be observed as well as the discontinuity in the concentration introduced by the solubility.

For comparison purposes, the same channel has been simulated with the same system level approach than the one used for the DCLL model. In this case, instead of MHD boundary layer a classic thermal boundary layer have been used [25]. The comparison of the results for $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol/m}^3$ are exposed in table 2

The permeation rate obtained with the system level model deviates 13.46 % from the result obtained with the 3D model. This deviation is caused by the approximations introduced in the system level model

Figure 9. Concentration contours at the middle section of the channel

Figure 10. Concentration of tritium next to the EUROFER wall

Table 2. Comparison between the 3D model and system model results for a PbLi channel

	3D model	System level
Inventory PbLi (g)	0.135	0.135
Inventory EUROFER (g)	0.024	0.022
Permeation Rate (g/s)	$1.009 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.732 \cdot 10^{-7}$

that cannot represent completely the geometry of the system.

6. Results

A reference case has been defined for a first analysis of the model results. Input values come from the design parameters of the DCLL [6, 14]. However, the model is not restricted to a single scenario and it accepts different input data thus, parametric studies can be performed. The input parameters of the reference case are summarized in table 3.

Since the ramps of the DEMO pulses have not been defined yet, as a first approach a generation pulse with 2 hours of burn time and 40 minutes of dwell time has been used. This implies that the real generation rate is only 75% of the full generation rate, i.e 188.5

Table 3. Main input data for the reference case

Parameter	Value
Fusion power; P(MW)	1572.0
Toroidal magnetic field; B ₀ (T)	5.0
Tritium Breeding Ratio; TBR(-)	1.13
Full generation rate; G(g/day)	251.3
Generation profile parameter; p(g/day m ³)	0.62
Generation profile parameter; b (m ⁻¹)	3.0
Generation profile parameter; ω (m)	0.0
Pulse length; τ _p (min)	120.0
Dwell time; τ _d (min)	40.0
PbLi mass flow rate per module; W _{mod} (kg/s)	49.2
PbLi Inlet temperature; T _{in} (°C)	300.0
PbLi Outlet temperature; T _{out} (°C)	550.0
Helium pressure; P(MPa)	8.0
TES efficiency ; η(%)	80.0
Heat exchanger volume; V _{HX} (m ³)	31.7
Heat exchanger surface; S _{HX} (m ²)	21.8

g/day.

Before simulating the reference case, one calculation of a single lead-lithium channel has been performed. The objective of this previous study is to analyse the impact of the FCI on tritium permeation. Figure 11 depicts the permeation of tritium from the bulk flow of a lead-lithium channel to the FCI that surrounds it during a few hours of full generation. Two different phenomena can be observed in this figure. Firstly, the permeation is faster through the Hartmann layers than through the side layers. This is a consequence of the difference between the layers thickness. Secondly, the permeation rate goes to zero after a few hours. This is because the alumina, which has a very low permeability [17], is acting as a very efficient permeation barrier. During the first hours, tritium permeates from the bulk flow to the internal EUROFER layer of the FCI. However, the layer saturates relatively quick because of the alumina barrier and at this point no more tritium is able to permeate.

The consequence of these results is that, in terms of tritium transport, the bulk flow and the gap flow are isolated from each other. Therefore, only the tritium generated inside the gaps of the channels is susceptible to permeate to the helium circuit. Tritium dissolved in the core flow of the channels and tritium trapped inside the FCIs only contributes to the tritium inventory.

6.1. Reference case

Several results have been obtained for the reference case. Moreover, because of the important impact that the FCI can potentially have on tritium permeation, one secondary model has been considered. In this second case the same input parameters and PFDs have been used but none of the lead-lithium channels contain FCIs. Figure 12 shows the inventory of tritium

Figure 11. Permeation from the core of one PbLi channel to the FCI through the Hartmann and side layers showing the permeation rates in the left axis and the total amount of tritium permeated in the right axis

in the DCLL blanket for the reference case compared with the case without FCIs.

Figure 12. (up) Total inventory of tritium in the whole system. (down) Part of the inventory located in the EUROFER (walls and EUROFER FCIs layers)

Due to the pulsed generation, the total inventory oscillates between the 768 mg and 66 mg. Those values correspond to the end of the burn time and the end of the dwell time, respectively. The inventory

is considerably smaller than those obtained for other liquid metal based blankets concepts [2,26]. The reason is the high PbLi mass flow rate of the DCLL concept. This high number increases the number of circulations of lead-lithium through the TES per unit time. Consequently, the extraction rate of tritium is boosted and the inventory remains in low values.

Regarding permeation, small inventories imply a relatively low permeation from the lead-lithium gaps to the helium channels. Results for tritium permeation from the lead-lithium to the helium for the whole DCLL blanket are shown in figure 13. Moreover, the model calculates a negligible permeation in the heat exchanger due to the high PbLi mass flow rates in this ancillary system (> 1 ton/s) in comparison with those inside the blanket channels.

Figure 13. Total permeation (right axis) and permeation rates(left axis) from the lead-lithium gaps to the helium circuits inside the DCLL blanket

Contrary to what it was expected at first, figure 13 shows that the FCIs have a little but detrimental effect over tritium permeation. The gap between the FCI and the wall constitutes a small volume of lead-lithium close to a considerable large permeation surface. In addition, the flow rates of the liquid metal at the gaps are much smaller than in the core of the channel. As a consequence, when the FCIs are considered the tritium concentration close to the walls is slightly bigger than the case without FCIs.

Quantitatively, the difference between both cases is small; the permeation rate oscillates around 1.66 mg/h in the reference case and around 1.58 mg/h in the case without FCIs. The tritium permeated to the coolant constitutes 0.031% and 0.028% of the tritium generated in the reference case and in the case without FCIs, respectively. In both cases, almost the rest of the tritium generated (more than 99.9%) is extracted by the TES with the exception of the tritium inventory located in the structural materials, the FCIs and the lead-lithium.

6.2. Parametric studies

Three parametric studies have been performed by varying three different parameters: the mass flow rate of lead lithium and the extraction efficiency (η) of the TES, and the T solubility in lead-lithium. In the every case the rest of the parameters are fixed. The extraction ratio, the inventory ratio and the permeation ratio have been obtained. The three ratios are defined with respect to the total tritium generated in the blanket (188.5 g/day).

Figure 14. Extraction ratio, permeation ratio and inventory ratio after one day of operation as a function of the mass flow rate of lead-lithium per module

Figure 14 presents the influence of the lead-lithium mass flow rate over the tritium behavior. Increasing the mass flow rate makes tritium extraction more effective due to the raise of the number of circulations through the TES per day. A higher extraction rate translates into a smaller inventory. Naturally, a smaller inventory implies smaller concentrations of tritium inside the liquid metal which generates smaller concentration gradients. As a consequence, a lower permeation of tritium is obtained for higher mass flow rates.

In figure 14 the uncertainty that the lead-lithium flow rate introduces in the model results can be analyzed. If for any reason the mass flow is not equally distributed between the modules and the channels or the pumping power fails in maintaining the pressure, the permeation of tritium will grow at the expense of the extraction. For small flow rate deviations around the reference case value, the uncertainty in the permeation is relatively small. For instance, for a relative decrease of 25% in the flow rate, a 35% relative increase of permeation ratio is observed. In more dramatic scenarios, for flow losses of dozens of kg/s the permeation of tritium doubles or triples its value with respect to the reference case value.

Regarding the extraction efficiency study, the results shown in figure 15 are qualitatively similar to

Figure 15. Extraction ratio, permeation ratio and inventory ratio after one day of operation as a function of the extraction efficiency η

those of figure 14. This is because an increase of any of the two parameters boosts the extraction rate. In this model 100% of the lead-lithium is processed by the TES. In addition, the TES is defined as an ideal system ruled by (9). Under these conditions, the extraction of tritium is very effective due to the huge mass flow rate of lead-lithium that circulates through the TES per unit time. Figure 15 shows that it is not necessary to have a high extraction efficiency η to have a good extraction rate as long as the TES can process the majority of the PbLi flow. Results show that with an extraction efficiency of a 30% it is possible to extract around the 99% of the tritium generated.

The extraction parameter introduces a very unlike uncertainty in the model results. For values of the extraction efficiency higher than 40%, there is relatively little uncertainty. However, for lower values of the extraction efficiency, the extraction rate falls rapidly. In this range ($\eta < 30\%$), a 20 % decrease of the extraction efficiency causes a 5% relative decrease of the extraction ratio while the permeation ratio experiments a 80% relative growth.

The last sensitivity study is related to the tritium solubility in lead-lithium. This parameter plays a very important role in tritium permeation but there is a considerable dispersion in the experimental measurements available in literature. As mentioned, the reference scenario considers the lowest value available for this constant [19]. In [27] a value one order of magnitude higher than the last one was measured, being one of the highest measurements available in literature. The sensitivity analysis compares the model results obtained when using both values of the solubility.

Figure 16 and figure 17 shows the heavy impact that the tritium solubility in lead-lithium has over the permeation rate. Both solubility constants differs in one order of magnitude which is directly

Figure 16. (up) Tritium inventory inside PbLi for two extreme values of T solubility in PbLi. (down) Tritium inventory inside EUROFER materials for two extreme values of T solubility in PbLi

Figure 17. (up) Permeation rate from PbLi flow to the helium circuit for two extreme values of T solubility in PbLi

translated into one order of magnitude difference in the tritium inventory inside EUROFER. Besides, the small concentration in the steel causes a three order of magnitude difference for the permeation rate to the helium circuit. Of the three studied parameters, the PbLi solubility is the one that introduces more uncertainty in the permeation rate results.

7. Conclusions and next steps

A tritium transport model at system level for the EU-DCLL breeding blanket has been developed. Results have been also obtained for a hypothetical DCLL blanket without FCIs. Besides, a parametric study of two critical parameters, the mass flow rate of

lead-lithium and the extraction efficiency, has been performed.

Simulations show that the enormous mass flow rate that characterizes the DCLL concept added to an extraction system able to process the 100% of the flow are the sources of a very high extraction rate. These also cause comparatively low inventories and permeation rates. Indeed, for the reference case, after 2 days more than 99.9% of the tritium generated is extracted by the TES while just 0.031% of the tritium ends up in the helium coolant circuit.

The effect of the FCI on tritium permeation has been analyzed. It has been found that even though the alumina is an effective permeation barrier, the presence of the lead-lithium gap has a detrimental effect on tritium permeation to the helium circuit.

The sensitivity analyses performed shows the important effect that experimental and design uncertainties have over the model results. Specially, the tritium solubility in lead-lithium whose value could change the permeation rate in three order magnitude.

Besides the uncertainties introduced by the input data, the model has an uncertainty caused by assumptions and approximations made in its design. The 3D models constitutes a useful tool to validate the accuracy of the approximations of the system models. A comparison between 3D results and system level results have been performed for a simplified system and a 13.46% difference in the permeation rate was obtained. This difference can be higher in more complex geometries with more physical phenomena involved. In future studies, 3D transport models of some parts of the DCLL breeder module will be developed in order to improve the approximations of the system model and characterize and reduce this uncertainty. This will be specially important in some critical areas like the lead-lithium gaps where the MHD effects can create a non trivial velocity distribution.

Future tasks of the EUROfusion tritium modeling work package [1] include the implementation of a more complex model at system level for the DCLL blanket. This model will be based on the updated DCLL design and will include more advanced descriptions of the lead-lithium and helium loops. The effect of other ancillary systems like an expansion tank and a storage tank will be included. Likewise, it is also of interest to implement a more realistic heat exchanger model when the design of this subsystem is available.

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